

EuroMix

European Test and Risk Assessment Strategies for Mixtures

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Proceedings and training material from second training session for stakeholders

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Deliverable D10.6

**Proceedings and training material from second
training session for stakeholders**

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Deliverable D10.6

Proceedings and training material from second training session for stakeholders

Contributors

Johanna Zilliacus¹, Emiel Rorije², Marc Kennedy³ and Jacob van Klaveren²

¹Karolinska Institutet, Sweden; ²RIVM, Netherlands, ³Fera, UK

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Introduction

To maximise implementation of the new risk assessment strategies developed in EuroMix, training has been given for the stakeholders who will use the new tools and models. The aim of the training sessions is that the stakeholders will gain understanding of the scientific basis behind the new risk assessment strategies, be able to use the developed tools and to interpret and assess the output as well as implement the strategies in their own context. Two training sessions have been organised. The first training session was given in February-March 2017. The second training session was given in February-May 2019 as a web-based training for EuroMix partners, two face-to-face trainings for stakeholders and five web-based trainings for stakeholders. A face-to-face training at EFSA is planned after the end of the project.

Web-based training for EuroMix partners

The web-based training for EuroMix partners was on February 13, 2019 using the GoToMeeting platform provided by RIVM. The participants could write questions in the chat function and also speak. Johanna Zilliacus, Karolinska Institutet, Sweden, Jacob van Klaveren and Emiel Rorije, RIVM, the Netherlands were trainers.

The aim of the training was to demonstrate the use of the EuroMix toolbox for mixture risk assessment and to carry out a trial run before the face-to-face trainings. The programme included presentations and exercises using the EuroMix toolbox that the participants performed after each presentation and that were discussed. Login details for the EuroMix toolbox and training material was provided to the participants before the training. The webinar was recorded and posted on the EuroMix share to give the opportunity for all participants to follow the training.

Programme

9.30-9.45	Welcome and introduction to the training, practical issues, aim of training, Johanna Zilliacus, Jacob van Klaveren
9.45-10.00	EuroMix approach for mixture risk assessment and for testing of substances, Johanna Zilliacus
10.00-10.30	EuroMix toolbox , Jacob van Klaveren
10.30-11.15	Exposure assessment in EuroMix toolbox, Jacob van Klaveren
11.15-11.45	Participants try out exposure assessment exercise, including coffee break
11.45-12.00	Questions and feedback from participants on the exposure assessment exercise
12.00-13.00	Lunch break
13.00-13.20	Grouping based on QSAR in EuroMix toolbox, Emiel Rorije
13.20-13.45	Participants try out QSAR grouping exercise
13.45-14.10	Relative potency factors from TTCs in EuroMix toolbox, Emiel Rorije
14.10-14.30	Participants try out TTC exercise, including coffee break
14.30-14.45	Questions and feedback from the participants on QSAR grouping and TTC exercises
14.45-15.30	Relative potency factors and dose-response modelling based on in vitro data in EuroMix toolbox, Johanna Zilliacus
15.30-16.00	Participants try out relative potency factors exercise
16.00-16.15	Questions and feedback from participants on the relative potency factors exercise
16.15-16.30	Conclusions, feedback from training, Johanna Zilliacus, Jacob van Klaveren

The training had 24 participants from 13 partner organisations.

After the training the participants were asked to fill in a web-based questionnaire that included the following questions:

- What was the most useful or interesting that you learned today?
- Exercise on Exposure assessment in EuroMix toolbox. Please give your feedback on the exercise. Was it understandable, useful, any questions?
- Exercise on Grouping based on QSAR. Please give your feedback on the exercise. Was it understandable, useful, any questions?
- Exercise on Relative potency factors from TTCs. Please give your feedback on the exercise. Was it understandable, useful, any questions?
- Exercise on Relative potency factors and dose-response modelling. Please give your feedback on the exercise. Was it understandable, useful, any questions?
- How do you plan to use the EuroMix toolbox after the training?
- Any additional comments or questions?

14 participants filled in the questionnaire. The results showed that they had received a useful overview of the possibilities in the EuroMix toolbox and appreciated that it can be applied for several steps in a mixture risk assessment. The presentations and exercises were in general understandable and useful, although more time for some of the exercises would have been needed. The feedback from the participants was used to fine-tune the presentations and exercises for the face-to-face stakeholder training.

Face-to-face trainings for stakeholders

The face-to-face trainings for stakeholders were on March 11 and 12, 2019 at Hilton Amsterdam Airport Schiphol hotel, The Netherlands. The same training was provided on each day with different participants. The aim of the training was to provide 1) Understanding of the EuroMix approach for improving mixture risk assessment, in line with international guidance and 2) Hands on training in the use of the EuroMix toolbox for mixture risk assessment.

The programme included presentations and exercises using the EuroMix toolbox. The participants performed the hands-on exercises in the toolbox as same time as the trainer presented. Thereafter each exercise was discussed. Login details for the EuroMix toolbox and training material was provided to the participants before the training. The participants were asked to bring a laptop to the training. Johanna Zilliacus, Karolinska Institutet, Sweden, Jacob van Klaveren and Emiel Rorije, RIVM, the Netherlands were trainers

10.30-10.45	Welcome and introduction to the training, Jacob van Klaveren and Johanna Zilliacus
10.45-11.15	EuroMix approach for mixture risk assessment and for testing of substances, Johanna Zilliacus
11.15-11.45	EuroMix toolbox , Jacob van Klaveren
11.45-13.15	Assessment of combined exposure in EuroMix toolbox, including use of TTC, Jacob van Klaveren and Emiel Rorije
13.15-14.00	Lunch break
14.00-14.45	Grouping based on QSAR for substances with lack of data in EuroMix toolbox, Emiel Rorije
14.45-15.00	Coffee break
15.00-16.15	Relative potency factors and dose-response modelling in EuroMix toolbox, Johanna Zilliacus
16.15-16.30	End of training , Jacob van Klaveren, Johanna Zilliacus

The trainings were announced by e-mail to stakeholders who have been identified to be relevant for EuroMix as well as on EuroMix website and EuroMix Facebook. The trainings on March 11 and 12, 2019 had 19 and 23 participants respectively. They were from 18 different countries and represented national and European authorities (including JRC and EFSA) (14), agrochemical, chemical, food and electricity industry (9), consultancy companies (2), universities (12), research institutes (4) and NGOs (1).

After the training the participants were asked to fill in a questionnaire on paper that included the following questions:

- What was the most useful or interesting that you learned today?
- What would you like to learn more about?
- How would you like to use the EuroMix toolbox after the training?

The results showed that the participants found that it was most useful and interesting to learn about the different functions and the practical use of the EuroMix toolbox as well as the methodology developed by EuroMix for mixture risk assessment. Many participants also highlighted the relative potency factor method and dose-response modelling, use of QSAR, TTC and in vitro data for assessments. The participants would like to have more practical experience of the EuroMix toolbox and on data to be used in the toolbox. They would like to use the EuroMix toolbox for different types of substances and exposures such as pesticides, biocides, food additives, contaminants and drinking water. Many would like to explore how the toolbox can be used for regulatory purposes and would like to explore the different options in the toolbox as well as discuss further how the toolbox can be used within their organisation.

Web-based trainings for stakeholders

Five 2-hour-long web-based trainings were given for stakeholders using the Zoom platform provided by KI. The aim of the webinars was to provide 1) Understanding of the EuroMix approach for improving mixture risk assessment, in line with international guidance and 2) Demonstration of the EuroMix toolbox for mixture risk assessment. The webinars included in addition to the topics presented at the face-to-face trainings, two new topics: presentation of the EuroMix handbook for mixture risk assessment and assessment of aggregate exposure using the EuroMix toolbox. Johanna Zilliacus, Karolinska Institutet, Sweden, Marc Kennedy, Fera, UK, Jacob van Klaveren and Emiel Rorije, RIVM, the Netherlands were trainers.

Programme

- May 6, 2019 at 14-16. EuroMix handbook for mixture risk assessment, Johanna Zilliacus
- May 7, 2019 at 14-16. Relative potency factors and dose-response modelling in EuroMix toolbox, Johanna Zilliacus
- May 8, 2019 at 14-16. Using QSAR and TTC approaches in EuroMix toolbox, Emiel Rorije
- May 10, 2019 at 10-12. Assessment of combined dietary exposure in EuroMix toolbox, Jacob van Klaveren
- May 13, 2019 at 14-16. Assessment of aggregate exposure in EuroMix toolbox, Marc Kennedy

After the webinars the participants could get access to a login for the EuroMix toolbox and try out the exercises that were presented during the webinars. The webinars were recorded and posted on the EuroMix website to give the opportunity for anyone to follow the training.

The trainings were announced by e-mail to stakeholders who have been identified to be relevant for EuroMix as well as on EuroMix website and EuroMix Facebook. 89 participants registered to the trainings in total. The number of participants for each webinar was: May 6 (78), May 7 (64), May 8 (59), May 10 (63) and May 13 (62). They were from 28 different countries from Europe, Asia and North America. They represented national and international authorities (including EC, JRC, EFSA, WHO) (43), agrochemical, chemical, food, petrochemical, cosmetics industry (25), consultancy companies (3), universities (15) and NGOs (3).

Training material

The training material was prepared for each training and modified based on the feedback received. The final training material is from the stakeholder webinars. The training material is in the form of the pdf files of the following PowerPoint presentations that also include the exercises:

Appendix 1-EuroMix handbook for mixture risk assessment
Appendix 2-Relative potency factors and dose-response modelling in EuroMix toolbox
Appendix 3-Using QSAR and TTC approaches in EuroMix toolbox
Appendix 4-Assessment of combined dietary exposure in EuroMix toolbox
Appendix 5-Assessment of aggregate exposure in EuroMix toolbox

Please note that the pdf of the presentations are of low print quality due to the limitation of file size of the deliverable that can be uploading into Sygma. High quality files are available here:

<https://ki.box.com/s/ax0g61txomw9uvhy3esika9kfr59n3w>

Conclusion

EuroMix has delivered a successful face-to-face and web-based training for 155 stakeholders from Europe, Asia and North America from national and international authorities, industry, NGOs, universities and research institutes.

Appendices

Training material

Appendix 1-EuroMix handbook for mixture risk assessment
Appendix 2-Relative potency factors and dose-response modelling in EuroMix toolbox
Appendix 3-Using QSAR and TTC approaches in EuroMix toolbox
Appendix 4-Assessment of combined dietary exposure in EuroMix toolbox
Appendix 5-Assessment of aggregate exposure in EuroMix toolbox